

Conference Abstract

Population Dynamics of the European Mudminnow (*Umbra krameri*) on Great Rye Island: Challenges and Conservation Strategies in the 21st Century

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Abstract

Great Rye Island (Veľký žitný ostrov, Csallóköz) hosts the most significant population of the European mudminnow (*Umbra krameri*) in Slovakia. While this population exhibited relative stability during the first decade of the 21st century, it has experienced a continuous decline, with the core population now primarily confined to the Čilizský potok. The primary driver of this decline is climate change, characterised by increasingly dry and hot summers that lead to the complete desiccation of the mudminnow's habitats. Notably, similar drought conditions were observed in the 1970s and 1980s, suggesting a historical precedent for these fluctuations. In addition to climate change, the proliferation of stagnophilic invasive species poses a secondary threat to the mudminnow population. While the Amur sleeper has not yet been recorded in the area, other invasive species have begun to encroach upon the mudminnow's habitat. Furthermore, human activities represent a tertiary factor contributing to habitat degradation, rendering these environments unsuitable for the survival of the species. For the European mudminnow population to recover, it is essential to address both external environmental conditions, such as the occurrence of wet years, and the restoration of habitats to ensure long-term viability. This includes the elimination of invasive species and mitigation of direct human impacts on local ecosystems. Effective conservation strategies must prioritise these

actions to support the resilience and sustainability of the European mudminnow population in Great Rye Island.

Keywords

Umbra krameri, European mudminnow, muddy fish, conservation, Slovakia

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.